

A Picture of People's Behavior and Economy during the Covid-19 Pandemic

Lisbet Situmorang¹, Maria Yohana Sihotang²

^{1,2} Faculty of Social and Political Sciences, Mulawarman University

ABSTRACT: The group of people most vulnerable to the economic impact of the Covid-19 pandemic is the people with income generated from daily income. In addition, the positive impact of this pandemic is an opportunity for Indonesia to be able to strengthen the domestic economy because the government will prioritize and strengthen purchasing power in the country only so that investment remains stable. Therefore, this research aims to find out the picture of people's behavior and economy during the Covid-19 pandemic. The method used in this article is the study of literature, where a study whose research object is in the form of literature works, whether in the form of scientific journals, books, articles, or statistical data that have existed before. The nature of this article is descriptive analysis, where researchers provide education and understanding to readers. The spread of the Covid-19 virus has an impact both directly and indirectly on the community and certainly pays enough attention to the government. As for the impact arising from the Covid-19 pandemic on people's behavior and economy, namely social restrictions, people are required to wash their hands often, wear masks, people's incomes are decreasing, many economic activities are closed, the economy of the community and the region decreases, the market price of produce decreases, and basic needs are increasingly soaring from normal prices.

KEYWORDS: Behavior Overview, Community Economy, Pandemic

INTRODUCTION

The Covid-19 pandemic is currently the focus of world attention, where the spread continues to occur rapidly and widely. The first information from the emergence of this pandemic is from china. According to the Chinese government, the beginning of the virus that causes the Covid-19 disease came from a wet market that sells various kinds of foods that are commonly consumed by Chinese people such as rats and bats (Handayani et al, 2020). The virus shows a very rapid spread and has caused many deaths both in China and in other countries. On January 30, 2020 WHO designated this corona virus as a troubling public health emergency so that from day to day this case is increasing rapidly until on March 11, 2020, WHO announced that the spread of the virus that is happening as a Global Pandemic (Dong et al, 2020). The COVID-19 pandemic has spread around the world with a high mortality rate and economic losses.

In response to this, the government implemented restrictions with a *social distancing* policy by maintaining social distancing and avoiding crowds, then *physical distancing*, namely by maintaining a distance between people of at least 1.8 meters since early March 2020. The government's policy has drastically reduced the number of activities and movements of people in the cities and regions in the country. However, in fact, the government's appeal regarding social restrictions is considered ineffective in preventing the transmission of Covid-19. Therefore, some offices and industries remain open because they are urged by the necessities of life, many people continue to carry out their activities as usual. Then finally with the approval of the central government, the implementation of Large-Scale Social Restrictions (PSBB) began in the territory of Indonesia. According to Juaningsih, et al (2020) Large-Scale Social Restrictions (PSBB) are restrictions on certain activities of residents in an area suspected of being infected with covid-19 in order to prevent the outbreak from spreading.

With the PSBB, some community activities such as offices and most industries are prohibited from operating for a specified period, causing economic losses to the community. This means that Covid-19 has a huge impact on people's social lives, including the behavior and economy of the community, especially in Indonesia. The spread of this virus causes changes in people's behavior. Community behavior is an action or activity that affects the health of the community itself (Notoatmodjo, 2012). According to Wonok, et al (2020) Community behavior in preventing Covid-19 is the knowledge, attitudes, and actions of the community towards the prevention of Covid-19 itself. The community is expected to be able to carry out good behavior management during the pandemic. People here really must understand how to prevent the covid-19 virus properly. The surrounding government is expected

to provide education related to knowledge, attitudes, and good actions in the process of implementing covid-19 prevention. In addition, another thing that also needs to be considered is economic factors.

Economic factors are one of the most important factors in human life because they are supporting factors for national development because a good economic growth of a country can increase a national development (Hanoatubun, 2020). The community group that is most vulnerable to the economic impact due to the Covid-19 pandemic is the community with income generated from daily income (Iskandar et al, 2020). In addition, the positive impact of this pandemic is an opportunity for Indonesia to be able to strengthen the domestic economy because the government will prioritize and strengthen purchasing power in the country only so that investment remains stable (Hanoatubun, 2020).

In addition, the role of the state government is also very necessary for the sake of economic stability during society. The government is expected to strive to improve and provide the best things to support the existing economic growth more optimally. During this pandemic, with various efforts made by the government, Indonesia has not been able to significantly increase economic growth. Therefore, this study aims to determine the behavioral and economic picture of the community during the Covid-19 pandemic.

RESEARCH METHODS

The method used in this article is literature study, where a study whose research object is in the form of literature works, both in the form of scientific journals, books, articles, and previously existing statistical data. The literature is used to complement the research conducted by the author, namely regarding the behavioral and economic picture of the community during the Covid-19 pandemic and the type of data used by researchers is secondary data. The nature of this article is descriptive analysis, where researchers provide education and understanding to readers.

RESULTS OF RESEARCH AND DISCUSSION

This research was conducted to determine the picture related to the behavior and economic picture of the community during the Covid-19 pandemic. Based on the results of reviews from several studies, people's attitudes in preventing the COVID-19 virus are currently quite good. The behavior that is currently routinely carried out by the community is by obeying the rules that have been made by using masks, washing hands, using *hand sanitizers* to maintain a safe distance, exercising, self-isolation for those who travel out of town and who are sick, maintaining personal hygiene, doing some vaccines, and eating healthy and nutritious foods. Purnamasari & Raharyani (2020) in their research related to the level of knowledge and behavior of the community found the results that people's knowledge about Covid-19 is high, which is also based on the level of community education. According to him, the higher the level of education, the higher the level of knowledge related to covid-19, as well as if the lower the education, the lower the knowledge related to covid-19.

Then another research that also strengthens the results of the study is a study conducted by Yanti, et al (2020) which states that 99% of Indonesians have good knowledge, 59% have positive behavior and 93% have good behavior towards efforts to prevent Covid-19 in Indonesia, namely by *implementing social distancing*. Good attitudes and behaviors result from a good level of knowledge from society so that people apply their knowledge appropriately. In addition, this high level of knowledge is also influenced by the level of education of most of the respondents is higher education with the last education of diplomas and bachelors. According to Yanti, et al (2020) a person's high level of education will make it easier for a person to get access to information about a problem that exists (Yanti et al, 2020). Furthermore, another study that is also in line with the results of the same study is a study conducted by Clements (2020) which shows that the people of the United States today already have good knowledge and behavior about covid-19.

According to Wonok, et al (2020) the factor that influences people's behavior in preventing Covid-19 is knowledge, where the knowledge is obtained from information that carries a message that can form opinions to the community. This means that if a piece of information is strong enough, it can provide a basis for good behavior, one of which is behavior in dealing with and preventing the COVID-19 virus.

The Covid-19 pandemic that has occurred in the world, including in Indonesia, has caused the emergence of new habits and behaviors during society (Gannika & Sembiring, 2020). These habits and behaviors make people more protective of themselves by

applying rules in the prevention and handling related to COVID-19. The behavior is implemented by the community based on what they know about covid-19 prevention.

Suharmano (2020) in his research revealed that there is a relationship between behavior and prevention of Covid-19 transmission. Based on his research, Suharmano stated that corona virus infection or covid-19 cannot be treated, however, there are several steps that can be taken to relieve symptoms and prevent the spread of the virus, namely referring covid-19 sufferers to undergo treatment and quarantine in hospitals, providing fever and pain relief drugs that are safe and according to the patient's condition, encouraging COVID-19 sufferers to get enough rest, encourage people with COVID-19 to drink plenty of water to maintain body fluid levels. Suharmano (2020) in his research also found results that there is a relationship between attitudes and behaviors to prevent the transmission of Covid-19, where most people have a good attitude towards covid-19 prevention. In his research, some of the actions taken by the community in preventing Covid-19 include avoiding traveling to public places that are crowded with visitors, using masks when doing outdoor activities, routinely washing hands with soap or using *hand sanitizers* after activities outside the home or in public places, not touching eyes, mouth, and nose before washing hands, avoid contact with animals, especially wild animals, cover the mouth and nose with a tissue when coughing or sneezing, then throw the tissue in the trash, avoid being close to people who are sick with fever, cough, or runny nose, keep frequently touched objects clean and clean the environment.

However, some people did not implement some preventive and self-preservation behaviors during the Covid-19 pandemic. Some behaviors that are not implemented can be caused by lack of knowledge, one of which is also due to lack of education from the local government and from the level of education also affects behavior during the pandemic. Furthermore, people's behavior is related to negative stigma towards patients who are positive for COVID-19. During the COVID-19 outbreak, a social phenomenon emerged that has the potential to aggravate the situation, namely the negative stigma against a person or group of people who experience symptoms of covid-19, where they are given labels, stereotypes, discrimination, are treated differently (Dai, 2020)

Livana, et al (2020) in their research found that in the case of covid-19 patients, there was an increase in the number of reports of community stigmatization related to patients who tested positive for covid-19. In Indonesia, negative stigma that arises in the form of social behavior such as exclusion in patients who have recovered from covid-19, because it is considered that they can still transmit the virus, reject and ostracize people who move from one area to another, ostracize certain ethnicities and consider them carriers of the virus, ostracize health medical personnel who work in hospitals and reject corpses because they are considered to still have a virus that can be transmitted to others victims of covid-19. The negative stigma circulating in society has an impact on the behavior of existing individuals, including encouraging individuals to hide diseases in order to avoid discrimination and avoiding health care. In order to avoid unwanted things in the existing negative stigma, action is needed.

Actions that can be taken to counter stigmatization attitudes include spreading correct information based on existing facts providing support, spreading news that can play a role in reducing existing negative stigma, asking for stories and experiences from various ethnic groups to give an idea that their efforts to heal are all the same as combating rumors that lead to stigmatization with information that really works in reducing stigma negative in society. In addition to community behavior, another thing that is also in the spotlight during the Covid-19 pandemic is the community's economy.

The community's economy is the most important factor in a life, where economic needs are closely related to daily life (Yamali & Putri, 2020). People in meeting their daily needs need a strong economy. In this pandemic era, the government is required to regulate policies regarding the existing economy to ensure the community's economy. The community's economy will currently experience a long decline due to the spread of the Covid-19 pandemic is increasingly spreading in various regions. According to Sayuti & Hidayati (2020) in her research, it was found that people's incomes have decreased since the Covid-19 pandemic, where the rapid transmission of the virus with the number of fatalities that continue to fall made the government make policies to reduce the transmission of the virus. Some of the policies made by the government such as large-scale social restrictions and limiting people's space for movement so that socio-economic activities are also hampered. Then another thing that has an effect is that not a few employees are laid off because the economy is down.

In addition to the decline in the economic situation of the community related to income caused by the Covid-19 pandemic, another economic impact was also felt, namely related to the number of jobs available. The covid-19 virus outbreak affects various aspects of life, one of which affects employment (Bala & Dongoran, 2021). Based on this, the indicator to see the economic impact

is to look at the available jobs. Employment has decreased since the covid pandemic took place, causing many people to become unemployed. Then to overcome this, it is necessary to empower the community's economy.

According to Aprilianto & Widiastuti (2021) empowerment is a concept that was born as part of the development of nature, community thinking and culture that exists in social life. Aprilianto & Widiastuti (2021) in their research got the results that one of the community empowerments can be done with zakat, infaq and almsgiving. Then one of the ways that can be done in economic recovery to reduce and help the poor and in improving community welfare is with zakat, infaq and almsgiving (Ghofur, 2016). The distribution of zakat, infaq and alms assets is carried out to prevent the spread and deal with covid-19 victims as well as reduce the death rate and help the difficulties of people affected by covid-19. One of the economic empowerments that exists in several regions is interest-free capital loans for the community, especially for prospective entrepreneurs or small traders who need capital assistance for their business. This is also inseparable from the role of the government.

The government has issued several policies related to the economic situation due to the Covid-19 pandemic, namely by providing joint leave days, providing debt payment relief for MSME actors, and opening a *call center* to receive reports and complaints from cooperatives and MSMEs affected by Covid-19. Some of these government policies have been implemented well and are expected to be implemented or implemented by the community as well. Furthermore, in its journey so far, the central government and local governments have implemented the adaptation of the new normal order or what we know as *newnormal* in society (Mardiana, 2020). According to Muhyiddin (2020) *new normal* is an action to reduce or minimize the impact of a disaster on the community, especially related to Covid-19 by carrying out new habits.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

This COVID-19 virus is an outbreak that initially emerged from China which then spread widely to almost all over the world. The spread of the COVID-19 virus has an impact both directly and indirectly on the community and certainly pays enough attention to the government. As for the impact arising from the Covid-19 pandemic on people's behavior and economy, namely social restrictions, people are required to wash their hands frequently, wear masks, people's incomes are declining, many economic activities are closed, the community and regional economies are declining, the market price of produce is declining, and necessities are increasingly soaring from normal prices.

The suggestions in this study are as follows:

1. The government is advised to ensure that the Covid-19 vaccine reaches vulnerable areas due to lack of health facilities.
2. To the social media in order to provide information that can really educate the public in handling and preventing COVID-19.
3. To the public to be more disciplined in carrying out health protection such as washing hands and wearing masks and maintaining a safe distance.
4. To the public to be more open to diseases suffered such as when coughing or having a cold, immediately to check their health and self-isolate.

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